

broadcast in field water at 1.5 kg ai/ha 10 d after transplanting Jaya. Soil samples were collected randomly from treated and untreated plots 1 d before treatment (DBT) and 7 and 14 d after treatment (DAT). Culture media for fungi and bacteria were prepared and inoculated using the Ricker and Ricker (1936) procedure. Fungus colonies were counted 3 d after incubation and bacteria colonies 7 d afterward. Two subsamples of each sample were evaluated in the laboratory to determine mean fungi and bacteria population per gram soil.

With time, both fungus and bacteria populations were inhibited by all insecticides except ethoprophos, where

Population^a of fungi and bacteria in rice rhizosphere soil treated with 6 granular insecticides at Bhubaneswar, India, Jun-Dec 1983.

Treatment	Population ($\sqrt{x + 0.5/g}$ soil)					
	Fungi ($\times 10^3$)			Bacteria ($\times 10^6$)		
	1 DBT	7 DAT	14 DAT	1 DBT	7 DAT	14 DAT
Untreated	5.4 bc	5.0 c	4.3 d	1.5 a	1.7 d	1.8 d
BPMC	5.3 bc	1.9 a	1.5 abc	1.7 ab	1.4 bc	1.2 ab
Carbofuran	5.8 d	3.4 b	1.3 abc	1.8 ab	1.6 cd	1.5 c
Carbosulfan	8.7 e	4.8 c	1.9 bc	1.6 ab	1.3 b	1.3 bc
Chlorpyrifos	4.7 b	2.8 b	1.2 ab	1.9 b	1.5 c	1.2 ab
Ethoprophos	5.4 bc	1.6 a	2.0 c	1.6 ab	0.9 a	1.2 ab
Phorate	3.9 a	3.3 b	1.0 a	1.6 ab	1.5 bc	1.1 a

^aSeparation of means in a column by DMRT at the 5% level.

populations increased 14 DAT (see table). We are studying the long-term

effect of these chemicals on microflora. *J*

Plant parasitic nematodes in rice fields under freshwater and saline soil conditions in Orissa, India

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Rice is extensively grown in Orissa, from the saline coastal belt (SCB) to the

interior districts with freshwater habitats (FWH). An examination of 75 rice rhizosphere samples from FWH [where the electrical conductivity of saturation extract (ECSE) ranged from 0.75 to 1.60 mmho/cm and the osmotic pressure (OP) of the soils registered 0.27 to 0.57 atm] revealed associations of 20 plant parasitic nematode species. Twelve samples from the SCB (ECSE, 2.87 to

5.85 mmho/cm and OP, 1.03 to 2.10 atm) yielded 6 plant parasitic nematodes, 5 of which also prevailed in FWH. The frequency and density of nematodes prevailing in the two habitats were varied (see table). Of all the parasites, *Hirschmanniella gracilis* was the most adaptable followed by *Criconebella ornata*. *J*

Plant parasitic nematodes associated with rice under freshwater and saline soil conditions in Orissa, India.

Species	Freshwater habitat ^a		Saline coastal belt ^b	
	Frequency ^c (%)	Density ^d (no.)	Frequency ^c	Density ^d (no.)
<i>Helicotylenchus dihystra</i>	25.9	M - H	-	-
<i>H. crenacauda</i>	10.4	H	-	-
<i>H. pseudorobustus</i>	30.3	M - H	-	-
<i>H. abunaamai</i>	1.5	M - H	-	-
<i>H. ptercercus</i>	5.2	H	-	-
<i>Hoplolaimus indicus</i>	8.8	M	-	-
<i>H. columbus</i>	-	-	25.0	L
<i>Tylenchorhynchus mashoodi</i>	46.6	M - H	25.0	L - M
<i>Pratylenchus zaeae</i>	16.7	M - H	-	-
<i>Hirschmanniella gracilis</i>	61.4	H	100.0	M - H
<i>H. mucronata</i>	25.9	M - H	-	-
<i>Hemicriconebellus cocophilus</i>	2.2	L - M	-	-
<i>H. mangiferae</i>	0.7	L	-	-
<i>Criconebella ornata</i>	7.4	M - H	33.3	M
<i>Caloosia exilis</i>	18.5	M - H	8.3	L
<i>C. heterocephala</i>	2.2	L - M	-	-
<i>R. reniformis</i>	2.2	L - M	-	-
<i>Heterodera</i> spp.	1.5	L	-	-
<i>Aphelenchoides besseyi</i>	23.8	L	58.1	L
<i>Siddiqia citri</i>	3	L	-	-
<i>S. boshi</i>	1.5	L	-	-

^aECSE = 0.75-1.6 mmho/cm; OP = 0.27-0.57 atm. ^bECSE = 2.81-5.85 mmho/cm; OP = 1.03-2.10 atm. ^cOut of 75 samples from FWH; out of 12 samples from SCB. ^dL = light = less than 100 in 250 ml of soil sample. M = medium = 101-500 in 250 ml of soil sample. H = heavy = more than 500 in 250 ml of soil sample.

Black beetle — a serious rice pest in western Himalayas

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Extensive field surveys conducted in the 1981-83 kharif season showed that black or Bhatula beetles *Heteronychus lioderes* Redt infest the low-lying irrigated as well as unirrigated rice fields in western Himalayas. This beetle is a serious menace to both transplanted and direct seeded rice in irrigated and rainfed areas. Fields enriched with humus or supplied with a high quantity of decomposed or undecomposed farm-yard manure (FYM) are more prone to beetle attack. In such fields, 20-40% of damage to rice is done by these notorious soil-inhabiting pests. Seventy of damage depends upon the soil type, FYM applied, and the moisture content of the field.